

Diastereotopy in some 3,4-dihydroisocoumarins and related compounds

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Some complex situations of diastereotopy involving two methylene groups about a chiral centre are reported. In this regard, NMR data for protons at and vicinal to the chiral centre in eight different 3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (1), as well as eleven related compounds (2) are presented. In the dihydroisocoumarins (1) both methylene groups adjacent to the chiral centre behave as diastereotopes, except if the proton at this carbon is replaced by hydroxyl or methoxyl; in which case the ring methylene protons at C-4 exhibit only a singlet. On the contrary, the open-chain compounds (2) exhibit diastereotopy only for the methylene group directly bonded to the aromatic ring.

Spin-spin coupling in nmr spectroscopy provides useful information for establishing the structure of an organic compound. Geminal coupling may be observed between the protons of a methylene group provided that they are not chemically equivalent. Such a situation may arise if, for example, the methylene group forms part of a 'rigid' heterocyclic ring. The presence of a chiral centre in the vicinity of a methylene group may also cause non-equivalence of the two methylene protons in the ¹H NMR spectrum, a phenomenon generally termed as diastereotopic effect^{1,2}. The geminal coupling constant (J_{gem}) in a diastereotopic methylene group, besides other factors, may depend upon the HCH-bond angle and the neighbouring substituents². J_{gem} is generally negative and its magnitude, for sp^3 hybridised carbon with an HCH-bond angle of about 109°, lies between 11 and 17 Hz. If protons are also present on the carbon(s) vicinal to this methylene group, its two protons are further coupled to differing extents resulting in a complex NMR spectrum for the methylene group corresponding to an ABX_n or ABM_mX_n system. An even more complex spectrum is expected if two such methylene groups are present at the chiral centre. Thus it is of interest to note the effect of a chiral centre on the diastereotopy of two methylenes attached to it in the following ways: (i) one of the methylenes is part of a heterocyclic ring, (ii) both methylenes and the chiral centre are present in the same chain, and (iii) the vicinal coupling is switched off. These aspects are explored here in the context of the spectra of 3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (1) and their open-chain precursors (2).

3,4-Dihydroisocoumarins (1) are a fairly important class of naturally occurring compounds though usually found in small amounts. They have a chiral centre situated within the heterocyclic ring at C-3 and their precursors (2) have it at C-2' in the open-chain. Both 1 and 2 are expected

to be the representatives of ABX and CDM₂X systems simultaneously. In case the alkyl group attached to the chiral centre is methyl, the compounds should correspond to ABX system alone. Moreover, if the proton at the chiral centre is replaced by another group, the two systems ABX and CDM₂X should be simplified to AB and CDM₂ respectively.

R ¹	R ²	R ³	X		R ¹	R ²	R ³	
1a	H	Me	Me	H	2a	H	OH	H
b	H	H	Me	H	b	H	OAc	H
c	H	H	H	H	c	H	OAc	CHO
d	C ₁₀ H ₂₁	Me	Me	H	d	C ₁₀ H ₂₁	OH	H
e	C ₁₀ H ₂₁	H	Me	H	e	C ₁₀ H ₂₁	OAc	H
f	C ₁₀ H ₂₁	H	H	H	f	C ₁₀ H ₂₁	OAc	CHO
g	C ₁₄ H ₂₉	Me	Me	H	g	C ₁₀ H ₂₁	OAc	COOH
h	C ₁₄ H ₂₉	H	H	OH	h	C ₁₄ H ₂₉	OH	H
i	C ₁₄ H ₂₉	H	H	OMe	i	C ₁₄ H ₂₉	OAc	H
					j	C ₁₄ H ₂₉	OAc	CHO
					k	C ₁₄ H ₂₉	OAc	COOH
					l	H	COOH	H

Results and Discussion

In the light of the foregoing discussion it was noticed that, with one solitary exception³, diastereotopy in this class of compounds was not specifically reported at the commencement of our synthetic work in this area⁴. This work has provided most of the data listed in Tables 1 and 2

which are derived from racemic 3,4-dihydroisocoumarins and their precursors. Spectra were measured at 300, 350 or 400 MHz for solutions in deuteriochloroform with TMS as internal standard. ^1H nmr data observed for racemic **1e** and **1f** are in excellent accord with those reported for the naturally occurring (*R*)-enantiomers⁵. Data for compounds **1c** and **2l** are taken from the literature³ for comparison.

From Table 1 it is evident that the proton at the chiral centre C-3, resonates as a multiplet at δ 4.5 \pm 0.2 and there is no significant effect of the substituents R^1 , R^2 and R^3 on the spectral appearance, chemical shifts and coupling constants of various protons if X is a hydrogen atom. In compounds **1a**, **1b** and **1c**, where $\text{R}^1 = \text{H}$, the methyl protons appear as doublet at about δ 1.45 but in the remaining compounds (**1d-i**), the corresponding methylene protons at C-1' exhibit diastereotopy with a chemical shift difference of almost 0.17 ppm. This value is quite large as compared to that between 4- H_A and 4- H_B which is less than 0.1 ppm, and **1e** being an exception. It may be noted that in the compounds of structure **1**, the motion of the methylene at C-4 is restricted as a result of its incorporation in the heterocyclic ring, whereas the other methylene at C-1' may undergo rotation about the bond between C-1' and C-3. These two methylenes for which $\Delta\nu/J_{\text{gem}} < 10$ Hz, correspond to ABX and CDM_2X systems respectively. Since the signals of H_C and H_D give rise to complex multiplets, it is not easy to determine a suitable value of J_{gem} (C-D). On the contrary, a

two protons. An exact reason for this behaviour is not known but a possible explanation is that this may happen if H_A and H_B are isochronous or 'accidentally equivalent', making an A_2 system². In this situation, lines centered at δ 3.81 and 3.21 respectively, in the two compounds are representing an 'AB' system with J_{gem} (A-B) \gg $\Delta\nu$. Similar results have been reported earlier⁶ for what should be called an AB system, but in our case the system becomes A_2 merely due to switching off the vicinal coupling with H-3. It is worth mentioning that diastereotopy in AB systems is well-documented³. One final word about the extent to which the diastereotopic effect due to a chiral centre may be transmitted in a chain. In a recent investigation by one of the present authors, it has been observed in *N*-(*n*-butyl)-substituted-3-methyl-4,1-benzoxazepin-2,5-di one that the effect is transmitted to a methylene group as far as four bonds away from the chiral centre⁷, however, due to overcrowding of the resonance peaks, such an effect could not be established beyond C-1' in compounds (**1d-i**).

In the case of the open-chain compounds **2**, C-2' is the chiral centre and the methylene groups at C-1' and C-3' should behave as ABX and CDM_2X systems respectively. The relevant proton nmr data for compounds **2** are listed in Table 2. The compounds with $\text{R}^2 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$ could not be studied as they cyclised spontaneously⁴. The most interesting feature of the data (Table 2) is that the methylene at C-3' does not exhibit diastereotopy in any instance. Moreover, instead of appearing as a quartet or doublet of triplets, its resonance signal is a multiplet; compounds **2a**, **2b** and **2c** are exceptions showing a doublet for the methyl protons. This unusual coupling behaviour shown by the C-3' methylene protons may be attributed to the chiral centre at C-2'. The chemical shifts (1.58 ± 0.07 ppm) displayed by these C-3' methylene protons are not much affected by the substituents R^2 and R^3 . In all of the compounds reported here the

Table 1. Proton chemical shifts and other nmr data for 3,4-dihydroisocoumarins (**1a-i**)^a

Compd. no.	$\text{H}_\text{A-4}$	$\text{H}_\text{B-4}$	$J_{\text{gem}}(\text{A-B})$	H-3	$\text{H}_{\text{C,D-1'}}$
1a	2.75 (3.7)	2.82 (10.5)	(16.0)	4.47 (m)	1.42 (3H, d, 6.3)
b	2.87 (3.7)	2.96 (10.5)	(16.1)	4.61 (m)	1.47 (3H, d, 6.3)
c	2.96 (4.4)	2.85 (11.0)	(16.0)	4.70 (m)	1.45 (3H, d, 6.3)
d	2.78 (3.3)	2.87 (10.9)	(16.1)	4.34 (m)	1.65 (m) 1.82 (m)
e	2.75 (4.0)	2.90 (10.7)	(16.2)	4.50 (m)	1.64 (m) 1.82 (m)
f	2.81 (4.4)	2.87 (10.8)	(16.3)	4.51 (m)	1.62 (m) 1.76 (m)
g	2.78 (3.3)	2.85 (10.3)	(16.1)	4.35 (m)	1.65 (m) 1.82 (m)
h	3.81 (2H, s)	—	—	—	1.65 (m) 1.82 (m)
i	3.21 (2H, s)	—	—	—	1.65 (m) 1.82 (m)

^aValues in parentheses are coupling constants in Hz.

consistent value of 16 Hz for J_{gem} (A-B) is observed. The methylene protons at C-4 also couple with proton (H-3) of the chiral centre involving different coupling constants of 10.6 ± 0.3 and 3.9 ± 0.5 Hz. The one resonating at lower field shows the higher *J*-value, however, the reverse order has been reported for **1c**³. The most striking feature (Table 1) is the chemical shift data for protons at C-4 in compounds **1h** and **1i**. Here the proton (H-3) has been replaced by hydroxyl and methoxyl groups respectively, but with retention of chirality at C-3. This arrangement should simplify the ring methylene to merely an AB system. Now the methylene protons at C-1' remain diastereotopic but those in the ring exhibit only one singlet corresponding to

Table 2. Proton NMR data for open-chain compounds **2**^a

Compd. no.	$\text{H}_\text{A-1'}$	$\text{H}_\text{B-1'}$	$J_{\text{gem}}(\text{A-B})$	H-2'	H-3'
2a	2.55 (7.4)	2.75 (3.4)	(12.3)	3.69 (m)	1.18 (3H, d, 6.1)
b	2.62 (6.6)	2.84 (6.7)	(13.5)	5.07 (m)	1.18 (3H, d, 6.3)
c	2.91 (8.5)	3.47 (6.1)	(13.1)	5.09 (m)	1.26 (3H, d, 6.3)
d	2.55 (8.6)	2.78 (4.0)	(13.5)	3.64 (m)	1.59 (m)
e	2.72 (6.8)	2.82 (6.3)	(13.6)	5.06	1.55 (m)
				(quint., 6.4)	
f	2.78 (9.1)	3.63 (3.9)	(13.1)	5.12 (m)	1.65 (m)
g	2.84 (9.0)	3.45 (3.6)	(13.5)	5.17 (m)	1.63 (m)
h	2.56 (8.6)	2.78 (4.0)	(13.5)	3.65 (m)	1.59 (m)
i	2.71 (6.3)	2.82 (7.0)	(13.6)	5.05	1.51 (m)
				(quint., 6.5)	
j	2.79 (9.0)	3.63 (3.3)	(13.2)	5.12	1.56 (m)
				(quint., 6.7)	
k	2.85 (9.0)	3.48 (3.6)	(13.5)	5.14 (m)	1.63 (m)
l	2.59 (8.0)	3.02 (6.4)	(13.3)	2.76	1.17 (3H, d, 6.9)
				(sext., 6.9)	

^aValues in parentheses are coupling constants in Hz.

Note

chemical shift of the proton (H-2') at the chiral centre is a sensitive function of the substituent R². Changing R² from OH to OAc causes a downfield shift of about 1.5 ppm. Except in a few cases where the H-2' proton appears as a quintet, it is generally observed as a multiplet indicating more complex coupling pattern due to two vicinal prochiral methylene groups. The C-1' methylene exhibits diastereotopy in all of the compounds examined with a consistent J_{gem} (A-B) value of 13.3 ± 0.3 Hz. Again the two protons show different coupling constants for H-2', however, in contrast to compounds **1**, here the proton resonating at higher field generally exhibits a higher coupling constant. There is no significant effect of substituent R² = OAc, on the chemical shift values and their difference for the two protons; $\Delta\delta$ ranges between 0.1–0.25 ppm. On the other hand, there is a quite notable effect of substituent R³ on the chemical shift of the proton resonating at lower field. A further downfield shift of about 0.6 ppm for R³ = COOH and 0.8 ppm for R³ = OAc is observed.

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